

QUATERNION APPROACH FOR REGION OF INTEREST EXTRACTION

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ABSTRACT: The ability to automatically find region of interest in images is useful in the area of satellite remote sensing and its applications. The class of algorithms that find any object of interest with non-prior knowledge, tries to detect objects in images that stand out, i.e. are salient, by virtue of being different from the rest of the image and consequently capture our attention. In this paper the existing methods for extracting region of interest from stationary images are explored and aimed to propose the fast, efficient method for region of interest extraction that outperform the existing methods in terms of accuracy and computational complexity based on the quaternion frequency domain analysis. The framework of the proposed model rapidly generated the saliency map with the application of quaternion Fourier transform. The saliency regions are accurately detected with the levels of decomposition by using Gaussian pyramid algorithm and thresholding. The proposed algorithm reduces the computational complexity of remote sensing image processing by meeting the timing requirement

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OBJECTIVE

The objective of this paper is to first explore some of the important approaches to Region of Interest (ROI) extraction, features and their limitations. This paper then proposes fast, efficient algorithm for region of interest extraction based on quaternion frequency domain analysis for salient region detection i.e computationally more efficient and provides more visually accurate detection results.

1.2 MOTIVATION

In today's information society, multimedia contents such as images and videos have become very important. However processing multimedia contents is very slow and its computational complexity is very high. So how to process the multimedia information fast is a key technique that needs to be solved. Researchers have found out that most information is only from some key regions in an image. If these key regions are extracted and processed, the computational speed can be highly improved. Therefore, based on this idea regions of interest is developed.

In the past decades satellite imagery has been used successfully for weather forecasting, geographical

and geological applications. Low resolution satellite images are sufficient for these sorts of applications. But the technological developments in the field of satellite imaging provide high resolution sensors which expands its field of application.

Traditional approaches for extracting Region of Interest in remote sensing images are inaccurate and prohibitively computationally complex.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Many of the intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance applications need to detect potential targets or regions of interest (ROIs) in digital imagery. These ROIs can then be used to automatically call for further sensing or other action, to control intelligent image compression algorithms, or to direct further analysis for target identification and recognition. For example, satellite imagery could be used to cue a flight by an unmanned air vehicle for more detailed surveillance. Another possible application could send an image containing only the region of interest to a war fighter equipped with a low bandwidth link, over which transmission of the entire image would not be feasible. For any of

these processes, we first need to analyse the image data at the source. Psychological studies have revealed that humans detect regions of interest before doing any processing. It is observed that during active viewing, there are approximately three eye fixations per second, each occurring between saccades (rapid eye jumps during which vision is suppressed). It is observed that most people look at the same parts of a given picture, so that certain positions were repeated with high probability. The researchers also showed that computer algorithms could be crafted to find ROIs similar to those determined by people.

ROI detection has been studied for many years. Most algorithms use either feature based or object based

approaches. Feature based methods find pixels that share significant optical features with the target and aggregate them to form ROIs. These methods can capture most of the target pixels on the basis of optical feature similarity. However, not all target pixels have strong optical features, so the detected ROI usually fails to encompass the entire target. In addition, feature based methods cannot distinguish between targets, which can cause confusion in subsequent stages of processing.

Object based methods, on the other hand, detect ROIs at a higher level than the pixel-by-pixel approach of feature-based systems using information such as target shape and structure. Typical approaches include template matching and matched filters. Although these methods can assign a single ROI to one target, they are limited because they require many calculations, have difficulty detecting multiple target types, and are not reliable when applied to low quality images.

A region that draws attention is defined as a focus of attention (FOA), which is considered an ROI or a target. Several computational models have been developed to simulate the human visual system (HVS).

Itti constructed a model using a biologically plausible architecture, which was proposed by Koch and Ullman and is the basis for visual attention. Dai et al. presented a method involving visual attention into the satellite image

classification. A faster, more efficient ROI detection algorithm based on an adaptive spatial sub sampling visual attention model was proposed by Zhang et al. The above models have attempted to simulate the visual attention mechanism based on the HVS biological construction. In addition to the above biological models, certain other methods have been proposed. Achanta et al. presented a frequency tuned approach for computing saliency in images using low level color and luminance features and it generates full resolution saliency maps. By analyzing the log spectrum of an input image, Hou et al. extracted the spectral residual for an image in the spectral domain and proposed a fast method for constructing a corresponding saliency map in the spatial domain. A bottom-up visual saliency model, graph based visual saliency (GBVS), is proposed by Harel et al. This method uses a novel application of ideas from graph theory to concentrate mass on activation maps, and to form activation maps from raw features. In addition to such models, the visual saliency model is also applied to video compression.

Remote sensing images comprise high amounts of data. The biological models can simulate the HVS well, but they often lead to prohibitive computational complexity and not consider the characteristics in frequency domain. Further, human visual attention does not necessarily reflect actual concern in a remote sensing image. Additional researchers in different disciplines calculate ROI quickly, but they only consider the features of the image itself. It is easy to cause false or missing detection.

Thus, we propose a Quaternion Frequency Domain Analysis model for Saliency Region Detection. This model is proposed to improve computational efficiency and accuracy in ROI detection of remote sensing images. After the HIS transform, a novel frequency domain strategy based on quaternion Fourier transform is used to generate a saliency map, which is time saving and efficient. In addition, an adaptive threshold segmentation algorithm based on Gaussian Pyramids is employed to obtain more accurate shape information of ROIs. Experimental

results show that the proposed model is time efficient and accurate.

3. PROPOSED METHOD

This model is proposed to improve computational efficiency and accuracy in ROI detection of remote sensing images. After the HSI transform, a novel frequency domain strategy based on quaternion Fourier transform is been used to generate a saliency map, which is time saving and efficient. In addition, an adaptive threshold segmentation algorithm based on Gaussian Pyramids is employed to obtain more accurate shape information of ROIs. Experimental results show that the proposed model is time efficient and accurate.

In this proposed model, the input image is sub sampled by a factor of 2 twice to reduce the amount of data and is preprocessed using the HSI transform. A novel frequency domain strategy is employed to generate a saliency map. Finally, the detected regions are formed through an adaptive threshold segmentation algorithm based on Gaussian Pyramids to improve accuracy in target detection.

HSI TRANSFORM

There are two frequently used color models in image processing applications: RGB (red, green, blue) and HIS (hue, saturation, intensity). Because the HSI color space is consistent with the human color perception system and is better than the RGB color space, remote sensing images are often transformed from RGB space to HSI space. HSI based methods are often used due to their simple computation, high spatial resolution and efficiency. Given an image in the RGB color format, the hue component for each RGB pixel is calculated using the following equation:

$$H = \begin{cases} \theta & B \leq G \\ 360 - \theta & B > G \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

with $\theta = \arccos\{((1/2)[(R - G) + (R - B)]/[(R - G)^2 + (R - B)(G - B)]^{1/2}\}$.

The saturation component is given by the following:

$$S = 1 - \frac{3}{(R+G+B)} [\min(R, G, B)] \quad (3.2)$$

Finally, the intensity component is given by the following:

$$I = \frac{1}{3}(R + G + B) \quad (3.3)$$

It is assumed that the RGB values have been normalized to the range [0, 1]; the angle θ is measured with respect to the red axis in the HSI space.

4. QUATERNION FOURIER TRANSFORM FREQUENCY DOMAIN STRATEGY

The quaternion's were first described by Irish mathematician William Rowan Hamilton and applied to mechanics in a 3 D space. The first definition of a quaternion Fourier transform was by Ell , and the first application of a quaternion Fourier transform to color images was reported by Sangwine using a discrete version of Ell's transform.

First of all, the remote sensing image is transformed to HIS space by applying an HSI transform method. Next, using pure quaternion's , a remote sensing image can be represented in quaternion form as follows:

$$f(n,m) = H(n,m)\mu_1 + S(n,m)\mu_2 + I(n,m)\mu_3 \quad (4.1)$$

where (n,m) is the location of each pixel. $H(n,m)$, $S(n,m)$, $I(n,m)$ are the hue, saturation, and intensity components of the pixel, respectively. The choice of μ is arbitrary, but it has consequences.

A generalized complex operator is employed in the Quaternion Fourier Transform. $\mu_3 = \mu_1\mu_2$, $\mu_1 \perp \mu_2$, $\mu_2 \perp \mu_3$, $\mu_3 \perp \mu_1$. $f(n,m)$ is represented in symplectic form as follows:

$$\begin{cases} f(n,m) = f_1(n,m) + f_2(n,m)\mu_2 \\ f_1(n,m) = H(n,m)\mu_1 \\ f_2(n,m) = S(n,m) + I(n,m)\mu_1 \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

We calculated the quaternion Fourier transform as follows:

$$F(u, v) = F_1(u, v) + F_2(u, v)\mu_2 \quad (4.3)$$

$F_i(u,v)$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{MN}} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{-\mu 1 2\pi i \left(\frac{mv}{M} + \frac{nu}{N} \right)} f_i(n, m) \quad (4.4)$$

For $i \in \{1, 2\}$, $f_i(n, m)$ is calculated by (4.2). The size of image is $M \times N$. The frequency domain representation for $f(n, m)$ is $F(u, v)$. $F(u, v)$ can be represented in polar coordinates as follows:

$$F(u, v) = |F(u, v)| e^{i\Phi(u, v)} \quad (4.5)$$

where $\Phi(u, v)$ is the phase spectrum and $|F(u, v)|$ is the amplitude of $F(u, v)$.

The phase preserves many of the important features of image such as the edge information. But its ability to highlight features is limited so the power of position information should be boosted further by using Butterworth high-pass filter (BHPF) with high-frequency-emphasis to make frequency information higher from amplitude spectrum.

A 2-D BHPF of order n and cutoff frequency D_0 is defined as

$$H(u, v) = \frac{1}{1 + \left[\frac{D_0}{D(u, v)} \right]^{2n}} \quad (4.6)$$

where $D(u, v) = [(u - M/2)^2 + (v - N/2)^2]^{1/2}$ is the distance between a point (u, v) in the frequency domain and the center of the frequency rectangle.

In our model, $D_0 = 4\%$ of

the image size and $n = 1$. The formulation of high-frequency emphasis filtering is defined as

$$He(u, v) = \delta H(u, v) \quad (4.7)$$

where $\delta = K / (\sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (SMAP(n, m))^2 / (M \times N))$.

Through test, suitable K is 0.16. $SMAP(n, m)$ is the initial saliency map with $\delta = 1$.

The inverse Fourier transform is the following

$$f_i(n, m) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{MN}} \sum_{v=0}^{M-1} \sum_{u=0}^{N-1} e^{-\mu 1 2\pi i \left(\frac{mv}{M} + \frac{nu}{N} \right)} F_i(u, v) \quad (4.8)$$

The output image can be constructed in the spatial domain

$$f^i(n, m) = x(n, m)\mu_1 + y(n, m)\mu_2 + z(n, m)\mu_3 \quad (4.9)$$

$f^i(n, m)$ is converted to grayscale to become initial saliency map.

Fig: 4.1 Saliency map generation using Quaternion Fourier Transform

ROI EXTRACTION

A Gaussian pyramid is a technique used in final saliency map generating. Gaussian pyramid decomposition

will generate a series of images in which each image is a low pass filtered copy of its predecessor.

The low pass filtering is performed via convolution using a Gaussian filter kernel and down sampling operator. Let the original image be g_0 , which comprises C columns and R rows of pixels. The Gaussian pyramid algorithm can be described as follows:

$$g_k = \text{Re}(g_{k-1}) \quad (4.10)$$

For levels $0 < k < N$ and nodes i, j , $0 \leq i < Ck$, $0 \leq j < Rk$. N is the number of levels in the pyramid, while Ck and Rk are the dimensions for the k th

level. The k th level image within a 5 by 5 window can be identified as follows:

$$gk(i, j) = \sum_{m=-2}^2 \sum_{n=-2}^2 w(m, n) g_{k-1}(2i + m, 2j + n) \quad (4.11)$$

where $w(m, n)$ satisfy $w(m, n) = \hat{w}(m)\hat{w}(n)$, which is the generating kernel. \hat{w} must meet the normalization, symmetry and equal contribution constraints. The equivalent weighting functions in a generating kernel are similar to Gaussian functions. Due to reduced sample density, gk is smaller than g_{k-1} by a scale factor of 1/2. This decomposition algorithm generates the final saliency map. Our model uses standard deviation 3.5 and size 10 for Gaussian filter kernel.

After using a Gaussian pyramid, Otsu is used to identify the threshold. A picture with the total pixel number N can be represented in gray levels $[1, 2, \dots, L]$. The number of pixels at level i is denoted by n_i . The probability for level i is as follows:

$$\begin{cases} p_i = n_i/N (i = 1, 2, \dots, L) \\ \sum_{i=1}^L p_i = 1 \end{cases} \quad (4.12)$$

The pixels are divided into two classes, A and B (background and objects, or vice versa), by a threshold at level k . A comprises pixels at levels $[1, \dots, k]$, and B comprises pixels at levels $[k + 1, \dots, L]$. The probabilities for class occurrence are given by the following:

$$\begin{cases} w_A = \sum_{i=1}^k p_i = w(k) \\ w_B = \sum_{i=k+1}^L p_i = 1 - w(k) \end{cases} \quad (4.13)$$

The class mean levels are calculated by the following:

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_A = \sum_{i=1}^k ip_i / w_A = \frac{\lambda(k)}{w(k)} \\ \lambda_B = \sum_{i=k+1}^L ip_i / w_B = \frac{\lambda_T - \lambda(k)}{1 - w(k)} \end{cases} \quad (4.14)$$

where $\lambda(k) = \sum_{i=1}^k ip_i$, and $\lambda_T(k) = \sum_{i=1}^L ip_i$. λ_T the average of the gray values for the entire image, and $\lambda_T = \omega_A \lambda_A + \omega_B \lambda_B$.

The variance between two classes is as follows:

$$\sigma^2(k) = \frac{[\lambda_T w(k) - \lambda(k)]^2}{w(k)[1 - w(k)]} \quad (4.15)$$

Using maximum variance theory, the optimal threshold k^* is

$$K^* = \arg \max \sigma^2(k)_{1 \leq k < L}$$

Then we use this threshold to transform the saliency map into a binary mask, where ones refer to the ROIs. The final detection result (ROI) is generated by multiplying the mask in the original image.

Region growing is a procedure that groups pixels or sub region into larger regions based on predefined criteria for growth. However, it will spend a lot of time and can't detect some effective area of the saliency. The larger the proportion of ROIs, the longer it takes to establish the region growing. Though the region growing provides a better description of the ROIs, it has become the most time-consuming part.

To establish an accurate description, an adaptive threshold segmentation algorithm based on Gaussian pyramids is used. It solves the "fragments" and "intra-regional black spots" problems from traditional single threshold method, and it is highly efficiency.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS & DISCUSSION

To evaluate the performance of the proposed model, several experiments were conducted using remote sensing images. The experiment was designed to compare the overall performance between the Itti model, the Achanta model, the SR model, the GBVS model and the proposed model, including qualitative and quantitative evaluations. Our method is mainly applied to high-resolution remote sensing images. Natural Heritage Maritime Image taken from SPOT 5 Satellite Image -Tamil Nadu, India which offers a resolution of 2.5 m. Of this image, the sea shore is defined as ROI and should be detected primarily. The image regions typically include one or more of the following characteristics: rich edge and texture features, the brightness area and color highlighting area. The tests were conducted on Windows platform. The PC was equipped with Intel Pentium CPU G630 and 8 GB memory. The images were 2048×2048 pixels. The implementations of the other methods can be downloaded from, which can generate the saliency maps.

We simulate the ROI extraction process of each method by using the ways which the authors mention in their letters.

5.1 QUALITATIVE EXPERIMENT

The saliency map comparison experiment and the ROI description comparison experiment for each model of remote sensing image are shown in Figs.5.1, each method can detect these ROIs basically in high-intensity contrast. The proposed method presents a more accurate description of ROIs.

The model of Achanta et al., the SR model, and the GBVS model fail to detect fully salient regions. The detected regions of the model of Itti et al. contain too much background information. Experimental results show that our method can be used for not only the high contrast image but also the low contrast image. The strength of the proposed QFDA model can easily be determined. IMAGE 1: SPOT 5 Satellite Image Tamil Nadu, India

Fig: 5.1 ITTI Model

Fig: 5.1 ACHANTA Model

Fig: 5.3 SR Model

Fig: 5.4 GBVS Model

Fig: 5.5 Proposed Approach of Quaternion

5.2 QUANTITATIVE EXPERIMENT

The processing time of different models for different remote sensing image size is shown in Fig. 5.7 and Table-1 is the time trends for computing saliency map of different models. Table illustrates the detailed time comparison of computing saliency map for different image size among different models.

Compared with the results from the traditional models, the time used for proposed is shorter than the models of Itti et al., Achanta et al., and GBVS. In the SR model, the log spectrum $L(f)$ is computed from the down-sampled image with height (or width) at 64 pixels. Thus, the timeframe is shorter and changed a little. Overall, our method is very fast in dealing with mass-data remote sensing image.

Fig. 5.6 Time trends for computing saliency map of different models.

TABLE 5.1

Time comparison of computing saliency map for different Image size among different models (s)

Method	Image Size(N×N)	
	1024	1536
QFDA	0.15	0.26
Itti	3.87	6.61
SR	0.17	0.17
Achant a	1.14	2.13
GBVS	1.69	2.39

6. CONCLUSION

The Quaternion Frequency Domain Analysis model is proposed and validated in this paper. The input image is down subsampled then transformed to an HSI color space to increase efficiency for further processing. For computing the saliency map, a strategy based on the Quaternion Fourier Transform is proposed. Frequency domain information is considered in the method herein. The model uses an adaptive threshold segmentation algorithm based on Gaussian Pyramids to generate the detected ROIs, which is much more accurate. Generally speaking, the detection results for this model are visually and statistically satisfactory. This model solves the problem of computation efficiency for remote sensing image processing. It meets the time requirements.

7. FUTURE SCOPE

In the past decades satellite imagery has been used successfully for weather forecasting, geographical and geological applications. Low resolution satellite images are sufficient for these sorts of applications. But the technological developments in the field of satellite imaging provide high resolution sensors which expands its field of applications in target detections and processing of the huge volume image data. Hence the proposed approach to extract the objects of interest with less computation time and high accuracy can be applied to meet the timings requirements of real time applications.

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